
Unwana-abasi S. Udoh

STRATEGIC ANALYSIS AND STRATEGIC FORMULATION: IMPLICATIONS IN THE NIGERIAN PORTS AUTHORITY II

UNWANA-ABASI S. UDOH , Ph.D

Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
unwanabasi06@gmail.com
+2348023139391

Abstract

The study was carried out to forestall operational inefficiency, laxity, and ineffectiveness in the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA). The resource-based stream of the Business Development Theory was adopted as the theoretical framework for the study. The methodology used in this research was the Historical/Descriptive survey design. The methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. Two subsidiary objectives were set, such as: to broaden the minds of the participants, particularly some of the newly promoted ones who may not have been very conversant with the core mandates (the need for efficiency and effectiveness) of the organisation from the time of their employment; and, to refresh the memories of other participants that may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA. In order to elicit answers from respondents, two research questions were asked based on the subsidiary objectives above, with corresponding hypotheses to enable empirical verification in the study. The collected data were analysed using the class participation approach, involving a total of 60 participants: 40 managers and 20 general managers of the NPA. The findings of the study were also in two folds, upon which the two recommendations were based. The recommendations were that the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) should continue to conduct similar trainings for all its staff. Secondly, the Federal Government should, as a matter of urgency, embark on a periodic re-orientation of the entire workforce of NPA (from the lowest to the highest cadre of the agency), especially now that the mother ministry in which the NPA was domiciled has metamorphosed from the Federal Ministry of Transport to the Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy.

Keywords: Strategic Analysis, Strategic Formulation, Implications in and Nigerian Ports Authority.

Unwana-abasi S. Udoh

Introduction

During a five-day training programme for managers and general managers of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, from January 8–12, 2024, Top-Idea Global Resources divided the theme, "Strategy Excellence: From Strategic Vision to Tactical Execution," into smaller subtopics and had different lecturers address each one. On January 9, 2024, which was the second day of the training, Dr. Unwana-Abasi Udoh of the Department of Public Administration at Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Nigeria, spoke about a set of subtopics titled "Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation: Implications in the Nigerian Ports Authority I and II" (as modified). The aforementioned subtopics, Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation (I) and Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation (II), were split into two sections. The treatment of Part I and Part II took place on the same day. Put differently, the focus of Part I was "Strategic Analysis," whereas the focus of this Part II will be "Strategic Formulation."

In Lecture 1, we had earlier stated that, while strategic analysis refers to an evaluation of an organisation's work environment, strategic formulation is the process of establishing goals and determining the proper plan of action to achieve those goals. In this second lecture, more concentration will be on strategic formulation rather than strategic analysis, which had been fully treated in Lecture 1.

However, once the organisation has successfully completed its internal analysis, it needs to know about external factors that can be a hindrance to its growth. To do so, they need to know how the market functions and how consumers react or behave to certain products or services. Measuring customer satisfaction is a common external analysis method. PESTEL analysis is one of the most widely used external analysis techniques. The process one is most likely to adopt when using a PESTLE technique is relatively simple, and it is called **external strategic analysis**.

In this lecture, our discussion will be primarily categorised into the following segments: assessing organisational culture and structure in relation to strategy; understanding the business environment; conducting a PESTEL analysis (political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, environmental, and legal factors); industrial analysis and Porter's Five Forces framework; and competitor analysis and benchmarking. But before then, let's see what strategic formulation means.

Strategy Formulation

Strategy formulation is an analytical process of selecting the best and most suitable course of action to meet the organisational objectives and vision. It is one of the steps of the strategic management process. The strategic plan allows an organisation to examine

its resources, provides a financial plan, and establishes the most appropriate action plan for increasing profits. It is examined through a SWOT analysis. SWOT is an acronym for strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat. The strategic plan should be communicated to all the employees so that they know the company's objectives, mission, and vision. It provides direction and focus for the employees.

Furthermore, strategy formulation is the process of establishing goals and determining the proper plan of action to achieve those goals. An organisation uses strategy formulation to plan for success and make improvements to workplace strategies as needed. Strategy formulation is essential for achieving and measuring the attainability of goals. After creating strategies, an organisation typically educates its employees so they know the organisation's purpose, workplace objectives, and goals.

Levels of Strategy Formulation

There are three levels of strategy formulation used in an organisation:

levels of strategy formulation include:

1. **Corporate Level Strategy:** This level outlines what you want to achieve: growth, stability, acquisition, or retrenchment. It focuses on what business you are going to enter the market with.
2. **Business-Level Strategy:** This level answers the question of how you are going to compete. It plays a role in those organisations that have smaller units of business, and each is considered the strategic business unit (SBU).
3. **Functional Level Strategy:** This level concentrates on how an organisation is going to grow. It defines daily actions, including the allocation of resources to deliver corporate and business-level strategies.

Hence, all organisations have competitors, and it is the strategy that enables one business to become more successful and established than the other. Therefore, as earlier stated, we shall now begin our discussion on the basis of the following sub-topics: Assessing organisational culture and structure in relation to strategy; understanding the business environment; conducting a PESTEL analysis (political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, environmental, and legal factors); industrial analysis and Porter's Five Forces framework; and competitor analysis and benchmarking.

Statement of the Problem

As mentioned earlier, it is on record that the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) was vested with the responsibility to carry out the following statutory duties and functions: develop, own, and operate ports and harbours; provide a safe and navigable channel; offer cargo handling and storage services; maintain port facilities and equipment; ensure safety and

security; and develop and own property. But it is observed that this system had greatly hindered port development and curtailed operational efficiency. The ports became less competitive and a conduit to drain the meagre national resources. In an attempt to change this trend, the activities of the Authority (NPA) were commercialised and offered greater autonomy in accordance with the recommendation of the Technical Committee on Privatisation and Commercialization. However, this could not bring the expected improvement because of the public service bureaucracy and interference. It was later revised to its initial status.

But, in an effort to reposition and enhance the national economy, the Federal Government embarked on various reform initiatives in the public sector, which included the maritime sub-sector. This initiative was to foster an economy that is responsive, robust, private sector-oriented, and in line with international best practices. In line with the reform programme, the transactions commenced with the advertisement for Expression of Interest EOIs on the 3rd of December 2003, by the National Council on Privatisation, with the Bureau of Public Enterprises acting as the transaction agent. A total of 110 EOIs were harvested, out of which 94 were pre-qualified.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to diagnose the implications of strategic analysis and strategic formulation on the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA). The subsidiary objectives included:

1. To broaden the knowledge of the participants, particularly some of the newly promoted ones who may not have been very conversant with the core mandates (efficiency and effectiveness) of the organisation from the time of their employment;
2. To refresh the memories of other participants who may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment, with the core mandates of the organisation, and with the current economic realities in the country.

Research Questions

The following will serve as research questions put forward to elicit answers from respondents:

1. Why have some of the newly promoted participants not been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency?
2. Is there any need to refresh the memories of those other participants who may have

been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment, with the core mandates of the organisation, and with the current economic realities in the country?

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses were postulated based on the two research questions above:

1. Some of the newly promoted participants may likely not have been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency.
2. There may be no need to refresh the memories of those other participants who may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment, with the core mandates of the organisation, and with the current economic realities in the country.

Methodology

The methodology used in this research was the historical/descriptive survey design. The methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The data collected were primarily analysed using the class participation approach, involving a total of 60 participants: 40 managers and 20 general managers of the NPA. Whereas, the secondary sources of data included text books, publications, journals, and the internet.

Theoretical Explications

The theory of business development was adopted in the study. Although this theory has five (5) variances, namely: resource-based theory, complexity theory, complex network theory, statistical learning theory, and games theory, the resource-based theory was found to be the most appropriate and was adopted in this study.

Resource-based Theory

Resource-based theory evolved as a way to help understand how strategic resources and capabilities usually allow organisations to enjoy excellent performance. Since its emergence in the 1990's, the resource-based theory does gain--typically in action and with contention that the possession of strategic resources provides an organisation with a golden opportunity to develop competitive advantages over its rivals. Though remarkably, resource-based theory never became relevant in firms' strategic measures until 1980's; this was simply because of its framework concepts that have focused directly on external issues. At present, with strong indications recently, it is observed

Umwana-abasi S. Udoh

that resource-based theory has gained maturity of some worth that's to be adopted by scholars instead of resource-based view approach (Barney, 2001). Subsequently many scholars have themed out that somehow, that resource-based theory perspective was evident from the 1930's, involving the works of Barney which was comprehensively inclined by Wernerfelt's work, which thereafter presented the indication of resource position hurdles that are related to entry barriers in the positioning school. But according to several scholars, more work did suggest that the resource-based theory denotes innovative paradigm to businesses with backgrounds in 'Ricardian and Penrosian' economic theories that were agreeing to what businesses can make has sustainable returns on investment (ROI) and comparable, indicates that competitive advantages in turn can help the organisation to enjoy strong profits/revenue for reason that a strategic resource is classified to be an asset that is valuable, rare, difficult to imitate and quite non-substitutable and makeup to an extent whereby it will help organisation to develop distinct strategies that make the most of target opportunities and ward off threats to make profits (Barney, Wright, & Ketchen, 2001; Hunt, 2013).

Application of the Business Development Theories to the NPA Business Environment

The applicability of the business theories to the NPA business environment has made it possible to discuss and as well task several changes with strategic management techniques that occur in business performance processes from the early 1940s', engaging in various improving activities and functioning to boost organisations' revenue and key performing methods through strategic decision techniques such as downsizing, outsourcing, benchmarking, economic value analysis, total quantity management, re-engineering, and others in order to enable the business world to primarily do something differently with several business theories to develop business tools and techniques. Developing business tools and techniques is simply considered a centre of challenges that determine or makeup the applicability of business theories for organisations' management and executives, and especially for those operations of large organisations compared to small organisations in terms of the practicality of techniques and theories relevancies that would envisage long-term success for business operations (Drucker, 1994). In conclusion, Spulber (2009) argues that business theories as concepts have been an appropriate platform for observing everyday business operations, including large and small organisations, in relation to the theory of business as it connects with economics, technology, philosophy, and other subjects or fields to explain and predicting the nature of operational business efficiency and likewise focus on its applicability to the business environment that considers aspects such as;

- Business action plan
- Business-behavioural strategy
- Business structure method
- Market environment system
- Economics of scale
- Global business fiction
- Strategic dominance and competitive advantage
- Collective business system
- Balancing short-term and long-term pay-outs
- Defining good and bad capital
- Knowing what customers want to buy

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study is categorised into two perspectives, namely, theoretical and empirical significance.

1. Theoretical significance:

The research will contribute immensely to the existing body of knowledge, and as such, it will serve as reference material for future researchers, both in the NPA and in the entire public sector generally.

2. Empirical significance:

The knowledge acquired from the study on the implications of strategic analysis and strategic formulation in the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) will help to proffer a lasting solution to the recurrent problem of inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the NPA. It is hoped that the actual cause of inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the organisation will be identified in the course of this research. Therefore, this study will offer experts solution to nip the problem on the board. The Legislature will find this material useful in making relevant legislation that will preserve NPA infrastructure and promote and revitalise the entire corporation as well as other government agencies. The executive will realise the importance of preserving government equity share in the organisation and, as such, will beef up strict supervision and security on the agency.

Definition of Concepts

- 1. Strategic Analysis:** Strategic analysis refers to an evaluation of an organisation's work environment.
- 2. Strategic Formulation:** Strategic formulation is the process of establishing goals and determining the proper plan of action to achieve those goals.

3. **Implications:** The term "implications" refers to the impact or effects (positive or negative) on a phenomenon. Implications may also refer to what something implies, means, or stands for (Udoh *et al.*, 2023).
4. **Nigerian Ports Authority:** The Nigerian Ports Authority is an agency or corporation of the Federal Government of Nigeria vested with the responsibility to develop, own, and operate ports and harbours; provide a safe and navigable channel; offer cargo handling and storage services; maintain port facilities and equipment; ensure safety and security; and develop and own property.

1. Assessing Organisational Culture and Structure in Relation to Strategy

Every organisation has its own culture and structure that will drive the core mandates of the organisation to an enviable height. The core mandates of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) have been clearly outlined in Lecture I.

In order to achieve the organisation's core mandates, both the culture and structure of the organisation must conform to the strategy or strategies with which the organisational mandates are carried out. Below are some steps that can be followed to successfully implement or execute organisational mandates.

Six (6) Steps to Execute Strategy Formulation

When formulating a strategy, consider the following steps:

i. Develop a strategic mission.

A strategic mission is a foundational statement that includes the organisation's values and long-term goals. To identify your company values, think of practices you would like to see your employees implementing on a daily basis. A strategic mission is a high-level understanding of a company's purpose and philosophies, and it can guide your strategies. The three major components of a strategic mission are as follows:

- **Time:** Think of where you'd like the business to be in one, five, and 10 years from now. Having a long-term perspective can help you identify aspects of your strategic mission that may involve your target market, customers, and challenges.
- **Core values:** Understanding core values can help you decide how to achieve goals and identify why you're working towards achieving these goals, how they could affect the company, and what outcome they may produce. A mission often includes core values that have a deeper meaning for the organisation.
- **Business description:** A description of what the organisation does and hopes to achieve can also assist with developing a strategic mission. Ask yourself what industry your organisation is in, what you hope to create, and how you plan to sell your goods or services.

Umwana-abasi S. Udoh

ii. Establish organisational goals.

Organisational goals are actionable objectives that can bring your team closer to achieving your strategic mission and improving your operations. Understanding what you're working towards can help you develop appropriate processes and procedures to reach your business goals efficiently. To identify organisational goals, consider the following factors:

- **Target market:** This factor identifies a specific demographic and market an organisation would like to sell its products or services to.
- **Customers:** Identifying the purchasing habits and behaviours of target customers is a large part of developing a business goal, so consider how they might use your product and what factors guide purchasing decisions.
- **Offerings or goods:** Reflect on how you can distinguish and improve your products or services, explore the benefits of your offerings, and determine what price point is best to sell the products or services.
- **Adaptation to changes and challenges:** Anticipating obstacles and planning solutions to them can help an organisation develop a plan of action to mitigate risk and excel.

iii. Create departmental plans

Then, you can dissect your goals and develop a plan for each department, team, or business unit. This helps you create tasks for employees to reach company goals and improve key performance indicators (KPIs). At this stage, you can establish numerical targets that you aim for or establish practical goals towards which you can take action. Here are some examples of departmental goals:

- Develop and use a customer database.
- Improve workplace safety.
- Invest in customer management.
- Convert more than 10 leads per month.
- Increase company revenue by 15%.

iv. Conduct a performance analysis

After gaining perspective on what to achieve, an organisation might conduct a performance analysis of internal and external departments to assess its current performance. This may help you learn if the organisation is competitive and valuable, if its goals are attainable, and if it aligns with trends in the industry. An analysis can reveal gaps between your stasis and your goals, and it may help you determine what techniques are the best fit for your needs.

One common type of analysis you might perform is a SWOT analysis, which investigates the following:

- **S:** Strengths
- **W:** Weaknesses
- **O:** Opportunities for growth
- **T:** Threats to the business

A SWOT analysis helps you objectively assess your current operations while also making future plans. You can use this tool to identify risks, implement management procedures and policies, reduce errors, and develop realistic sales predictions. An effective SWOT analysis can help you implement proactive strategies to help you remain resilient.

v. *Implement a plan of action*

Define what methods you plan to use to implement your strategy. You can also make adjustments to your strategies as market or industry changes occur. It may be helpful to have regular meetings with management across all departments to discuss how the strategy applies to their team's work. Allocate business resources accordingly so each team can promote organisational goals. Some examples of strategies include:

- Creating a website to increase customer reach
- Implementing a new online advertising campaign to increase sales
- Using unique features for products to increase product differentiation
- Gaining a technological advantage by investing in new software programmes or technology devices to improve productivity and perform market research

vi. *Revise Your Strategy as Needed*

As you implement a new strategy to reach organisational goals, be sure to monitor your progress and consistently conduct analyses to evaluate the effectiveness of the strategy. Using metrics to evaluate the results of your strategy may help you make objective, data-backed decisions. Remember to monitor industry news and relevant financial markets so you can adapt your strategy accordingly. It's vital to set regular times to review progress and re-evaluate strategies, like every month, quarterly, or yearly.

2. Understanding the Business Environment

In order to understand the business environment, strategic analysis and market research, as well as various steps of strategy formulation, have to be properly dealt with.

a) *Strategic Analysis and Market Research*

It is necessary that we consider the concept of market research, which invariably means understanding the business environment. As important as it is, market research can provide you with the necessary information to know the different market scenarios and suggest strategies to achieve more sales. Market research is either qualitative or quantitative in nature. Market research can provide you with the necessary information to know the different market scenarios and propose strategies to achieve more sales. For example, through market research, an organisation can know the degree of recognition that the brand has and plan a marketing campaign correctly.

Organisations can also effectively introduce a new product into the market or innovate through the new ideas of customers. Ask the right questions to customers and get their feedback. The data provided by the investigation will help you to plan correctly what you have to do, for example, in case your competitors lower their prices or if there are changes in the behaviour of your consumers.

b) *Steps of Strategy Formulation*

The steps or processes of strategy formulation include the following:

- i. **Establishing Organisational Objectives:** This involves establishing the long-term goals of an organisation. Strategic decisions can be taken once the organisational objectives are determined.
- ii. **Analysis of the Organisational Environment:** This involves SWOT analysis, meaning identifying the company's strengths and weaknesses and keeping vigilance over competitors' actions to understand opportunities and threats. Strengths and weaknesses are internal factors that the company has control over. Opportunities and threats, on the other hand, are external factors over which the company has no control. A successful organisation builds on its strengths, overcomes its weaknesses, identifies new opportunities, and protects against external threats.
- iii. **Forming quantitative goals:** Defining targets so as to meet the company's short-term and long-term objectives. Example, 30% increase in revenue this year of a company.
- iv. **Objectives in Context with Divisional Plans:** This involves setting up targets for every department so that they work in coherence with the organisation as a whole.

- v. **Performance Analysis:** This is done to estimate the degree of variation between the actual and the standard performance of an organisation.
- vi. **Selection of Strategy:** This is the final step in strategy formulation. It involves the evaluation of the alternatives and the selection of the best strategy among them to be the strategy of the organisation. The strategy formulation process is an integral part of strategic management, as it helps in framing effective strategies for the organisation to survive and grow in the dynamic business environment.

3. **PESTLE Analysis:** External Strategic Analysis

PESTLE analysis (**political, economic, social, legal, and environmental**) describes a framework of macro-environmental factors used in the environmental scanning component of external strategic analysis. The model has been extended by adding **ethical** and **demographic** factors. It is a part of the external analysis when conducting a strategic analysis or doing market research and giving an overview of the different macro-environmental factors that the organisation has to take into consideration. By using PESTLE analysis, one can:

- i. Find out the key issues beyond the organisation's control, like changes in political scenarios and changing rules that can be implemented at any point in time;
- ii. Identify the impact of each issue;
- iii. See how important these issues are to the organisation;
- iv. Rate the likelihood of its occurrence; and,
- v. Briefly consider the implications if the issue did occur.

4. **Industrial Analysis and Porter's Five Forces Framework**

A profound understanding of the competitive environment is a critical ingredient in a successful strategy. Every business strategy is essentially a quest for profit. As such, it is necessary to identify the sources of profit in the external environment. The focus of environmental analysis is industry analysis. Industry analysis is relevant both to corporate-level and business-level strategy.

Corporate strategy is concerned with deciding which industries products should be engaged in and how it should allocate its resources among them. Such decisions require an assessment of the attractiveness of different industries in terms of their profit potential. It is therefore important to understand how the competitive structure of an industry determines its profitability.

Business strategy is concerned with establishing a competitive advantage. By analysing customer needs and preferences and the ways in which products compete to serve customers, we identify the general sources of competitive advantage in an industry—what we call key success factors.

On the other hand, Porter's Five Forces can be referred to as "a framework to classify and analyse the factors that determine the profitability of an industry" by Michael Porter, Harvard Business School (born 1947). Michael Porter's main theory is on competition and company strategy. He is generally recognised as the father of the modern strategy field, and his ideas are taught in virtually every business school in the world. Other subjects include competitiveness, economic development, environmental policy, and the role of corporations in society. Further, the model of the Five Competitive Forces was developed by Michael E. Porter in his 1980 book "Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analysing Industries and Competitor". Since that time, it has become an important tool for analysing an organisation's industry structure in strategic processes.

In a model by Porter (2008), five competitive forces (called Porter Five Forces) that shape strategy in industry competition are categorised into two groups, namely: vertical and horizontal.

Vertical Forces

- i. Threat of New Entrants
- ii. Rivalries among Existing Competitors
- iii. Threat of Substitute Products or Services

Horizontal Forces

- i. Bargaining Power of Suppliers
- ii. Rivalries among Existing Competitors
- iii. Bargaining Power of Buyers

Porter's model is based on the insight that a corporate strategy should meet the opportunities and threats in the organisation's external environment. Especially, competitive strategy should be based on an understanding of industry structures and the way they change. Porter has identified five competitive forces that shape every industry and every market. These forces determine the intensity of competition and, hence, the profitability and attractiveness of an industry. The objective of corporate strategy should be to modify these competitive forces in a way that improves the position of the organisation. Porter's model supports analysis of the driving forces in an industry. Based on the information derived from the Five Forces Analysis, management can decide how to influence or to exploit particular characteristics of their industry.

5. Competitor's Analysis and Benchmarking

In an abstraction by Adom, N.Y. *et al.* (2016) in their research on the topic "Competitor Analysis in Strategic Management: Is It a Worthwhile Managerial Practice in Contemporary Times?" that was published in the Journal of Resources Development and Management, the authors held that "the actions and behaviour of close competitors are essential". According to them, "unless a company pays attention to what competitors are doing, it ends up 'flying blind' into battle. Managers need competitive information to understand the industry and its competitors, to identify areas in which the competitors are weak, and to evaluate the impact of strategic actions on competitors".

The goal of their study was to find out if competitor analysis was still useful as a strategic management tool in today's business world. To do this, they used an integrative literature review method that combined reviews, critiques, and the synthesis of relevant literature to come up with new ideas about competitor analysis. The study revealed that identifying competitors and how they operate helps managers tackle industry issues that are detrimental to their companies' health and also helps managers to learn from competitors. It also revealed that firms that pay attention to competitors' actions have been found to achieve better business.

On the other hand, benchmarking has been seen as a measure of competitiveness and defined by a project manager at an IT company as "the measurement of the quality of an organisation's guidelines, programmes, strategies, etc. and their assessment with standard measurements or comparable dimensions of its peers". In today's highly competitive, rapidly changing global economy, organisations have been compelled to consider and implement a wider variety of innovative management philosophies and techniques. Benchmarking as a technique has been attracting considerable attention for its effectiveness (Yasin, 2002; Sisson *et al.*, 2003; Rohlfer, 2004; Anderson and McAdam, 2004; Huq *et al.*, 2008; Likierman, 2009).

Summary of Findings

Based on the two hypotheses postulated in this study, a participant enquiry method was adopted in the class by the lecturer, thereby affording the managers and general managers of NPA that attended the training the opportunity to interact during the interactive session. During the interactive session, it was found that:

- i. Some of the newly promoted participants have not been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency.
- ii. There was a need to refresh the memories of those other participants who may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their

employment, with the core mandates of the organisation, and with the current economic realities in the country.

Conclusion

There are many factors that can contribute to successful strategy formulation. It's important to adapt, allow for new ideas, and ask for feedback throughout the strategy formulation process. While planning a new strategy, it may be helpful for you to review *SMART goals*.

SMART stands for specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-based goals. SMART goals can help you craft a specific objective that's easy to measure or track and has a clear and concise plan for success. Using the SMART acronym as a framework for identifying organisational goals can ensure you're planning a strategy that can make your organisation highly competitive in its industry. Here's an example of a SMART goal for a business that plans to start new social media accounts to grow the customer base:

Catarina's Confectionary Creations Company wants to use social media to connect with potential customers. They plan to create 15-second videos to post on three different social media platforms, showing customers how they bake each of their products. They're aiming to gain at least 1,000 engagements and 250 followers on each site by the end of the month.

- **Specific:** The organisation states the exact measures they can take to achieve their goal.
- **Measurable:** They include numerical goals, so they can clearly understand whether they met their goal at the end of the month.
- **Achievable:** Since the organisation is new to social media, they set realistic goals for slowly building a follower base rather than expecting to go viral immediately.
- **Relevant:** The actions Catarina's Confectionary Creations Company plans to take are relevant to their overall strategy, which is to start using social media to attract customers.
- **Time-based:** The business hopes to complete their goal by the end of the month.

Finally, when formulating a strategy, gathering data from team members through internal surveys and interviews might also help you assess your operations. After creating and implementing a new strategy, ask your peers and employees how they feel about the strategy and its effectiveness. Promote an open communication policy and allow them to give their opinions and express ideas for alternative approaches and perspectives. Feedback can help you revise strategies and apply the ideas from employees who use them daily. Involving all employees in the strategy formulation

process may also help the teams feel connected to the organisation's efforts. You may also design many drafts of a strategy and how to use them. But ensure keeping a copy of each draft and comparing them as you adjust. You can use these drafts as a baseline to refer to while determining the relativity of each idea for a strategy to the goals you're trying to reach.

Recommendations

As a result of the two (2) findings made in the study, it was recommended that:

1. To increase personnel understanding, the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) should keep offering comparable trainings. This is because, based on the aforementioned findings, NPC must be aware that some recently promoted participants may not have been fully aware of the organization's core mandates regarding the necessity of efficiency and effectiveness in the agency during their employment, which may have contributed to lapses such as inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the agency.

2. The Federal Government should immediately begin a periodic reorientation of the entire NPA workforce (from the lowest to the highest cadre of the agency). This is especially important given that the Federal Ministry of Transport, which was the NPA's original home, has changed its name to the Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy. The reason for this is that during the course of the study, it became clear that it was necessary to refresh the memory of those other participants who might have been highly knowledgeable about the NPA's operations from their time as employees, as well as about the organization's fundamental goals and the nation's present economic conditions.

References

- Adom, A. Y., Nyarko, I. K., Kumi, G. N. (2016). Competitor Analysis in Strategic Management: Is it a Worthwhile Managerial Practice in Contemporary Times? *Journal of Resources Development and Management* www.iiste.org ISSN 2422-8397: *An International Peer-reviewed Journal* Vol.24.
- Anderson, K. and McAdam, R. (2004). A critique of benchmarking and performance measurement: Lead or Lag. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 11(5), 465-483.

- Barney, J.B. (2001). Is the Resource Based View a Useful Perspective for Strategic Management Research? *Academy of Management Review*. 26 (1): 102. doi:10.5465/AMR.2001.4011938.
- Barney, J. B., Wright, M., & Ketchen, D. J. (2001). The Resource Based View of the Firm: Ten years after 1991. *Journal of Management*, 27: 625-43.
- Hunt, S.D. (2013). A General Theory of Business Marketing: R-A theory, Alderson, the ISBM Framework and the IMP Theoretical Structure. *Industrial Marketing Management*. 41: 283-293.
- Huq, F., Abbo, M.-H. and Huq, Z. (2008). Perceptions about benchmarking best practices among French managers: an exploratory survey. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 15, 382-401.
- Likierman, A. (2009). The five traps of performance measurement. *Harvard Business Review*, 87(10), 96-101.
- Machiavelli, N. (1999). *The Prince*. Penguin Books. London, England.
- Porter, M.E. (2008). The Five Competitive Forces That Shapes Strategy. *Harvard Business Review*. Strategic Management – Eva Perea – UAO.
- Rohlfer, S. (2004). Benchmarking concepts in the UK and Germany: A shared understanding among key players. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 11(5), 521- 539.
- Spulber, D.F (2009). *The Theory of the Firm*, Cambridge. Retrieved on 27th January, 2024 from <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:cup:cbooks:9780521736602>.
- Udoh, U.S. and Udobia, U.J. (2023). Power Outage and Its Implications on Value Chain Along Aba and Itu National Grid, Comprising Uyo and Eket Metropolitan Cities in Akwa Ibom State. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities (GJCH)*, Vol.2, Issue 2, (pp.101-127).

Umwana-abasi S. Udoh

V., (1996). *The Mafia Manager: A Guide to the Corporate Machiavelli*. St. Martin's Griffin, New York.

Yasin, M. (2002). The theory and practice of benchmarking: then and now. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. 9(3), 217-243.